

Spectroscopic studies on the ligand field strength of some chelating agents

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o-Aminobenzoic acid and *o*-aminobenzoic acid hydrazide complexes with CuSO₄ and Cr₂(SO₄)₃ (2 : 1 L/M ratio) have been prepared. The complexes have been investigated using electronic spectroscopy in solid state. Gaussian analysis has been carried out on the Cu^{II} complexes. The complexes have octahedral structure. The ligand field strength of *o*-ABAH is greater than of *o*-ABA.

o-Aminobenzoic acid (*o*-ABA) forms highly insoluble complexes suitable for gravimetric determination of transition metals¹. Also these complexes are pharmacologically active as inflammatory agents². *o*-ABA transition metal complexes are reported in literature^{3,4}. Acid hydrazides are biologically active materials⁵ and important chelating agents⁶. Several transition metal complexes *o*-aminobenzoic acid hydrazide (*o*-ABAH) have been reported^{7,8}.

The Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes with *o*-ABA and *o*-ABAH ligands are reported here. The objective of this study is to compare the ligand field strength of *o*-ABA and *o*-ABAH ligands using electronic spectra in solid state. The study presents the Gaussian analysis as a method for separation of the overlapped peaks. Such separation enables us to calculate some spectral parameters to throw some light on the electronic structure of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Some complexes of Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} with *o*-ABA and *o*-ABAH (Table 1) were prepared with 2 : 1 ligand-metal ratio. The μ_{eff} values (Table 2) indicate that the Cu^{II} complexes contain one unpaired electron, while the Cr^{III} complexes have three unpaired electrons.

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands and their complexes*

Compd	Mol formula	Metal %
		Found/(Calcd)
<i>o</i> -ABA ligand	C ₇ H ₇ NO ₂	—
[Cr(<i>o</i> -ABA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₆ SCr ₂	14 00 (13 97)
[Cu(<i>o</i> -ABA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	18 90 (18 92)
<i>o</i> -ABAH ligand	C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O	—
[Cr(<i>o</i> -ABAH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ N ₁₂ O ₂₀ S ₃ Cr ₂	9 70 (9 73)
[Cu(<i>o</i> -ABAH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₈ SCu	12 80 (12 76)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis

Table 2. Physical and electronic spectral data for the Cu^{II} complexes

Parameter	[Cu(<i>o</i> -ABA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	[Cu(<i>o</i> -ABAH) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ SO ₄
Colour	Light green	Dark green
μ_{eff} (B M)	1 88	1 91
Peak positions (cm ⁻¹)	11952	11820
	13372	14085
	15466	16313
	17212	17762
<i>D</i> _q	1337	1408
<i>D</i> _s	2172	2144
<i>D</i> _t	652	648
λ	-1164	-966

The experimental and resolved optical absorption spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes with *o*-ABA and *o*-ABAH contain overlapping bands. Gaussian analysis using FORTRAN fitting program, was carried out to separate these overlapping bands. Each of the resolved spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show four bands (Table 2). The colour and peak positions indicate that these complexes are octahedrally coordinated. The result is consistent with the reported Cu^{II} complexes with *o*-ABA⁴ and *o*-ABAH⁸. The broadening in the observed bands reflects the distortion in these complexes, which can be attributed to Jahn-Teller effect⁹. Thus the interpretation of the spectrum was carried out assuming that Cu^{II} is tetragonally distorted in *D*_{4h} symmetry. The band assignment was carried out taking into consideration the splitting of *d*⁹ (²*D* is the free ion term) by environment. This splitting is much larger than that due to spin-orbit coupling. The band assignment was carried out considering the spin-orbit interaction. Thus, in the spectrum of *o*-ABAH-Cu^{II} complex, the third and fourth bands at 16313 and 17762 cm⁻¹ respectively, may be due to the transitions, $\Gamma 7^a(^2E_g) \rightarrow \Gamma 6^b(^2T_{2g})$ and $\Gamma 7^a(^2E_g) \rightarrow \Gamma 7^c(^2T_{2g})$.

According to conventional theory, the spin-orbit splitting of these levels should amount to about $\frac{3}{2}\lambda$ in first order¹⁰. The energy separation between the third and fourth

bands (1449 cm^{-1}) is higher than that of the free-ion value (1245 cm^{-1}). The large value of λ indicates that besides the spin-orbit coupling the complex is subjected to slight molecular distortion¹¹.

The other two bands which appear at 11820 and 14085 cm^{-1} are assigned to transitions, $\Gamma 7^a(^2E_g) \rightarrow \Gamma 6^a(^2E_g)$ and $\Gamma 7^a(^2E_g) \rightarrow \Gamma 7^b(^2T_{2g})$. The energy matrices for tetragonal crystal field inclusive of spin-orbit coupling for d^1 and d^9 are given by Liehr¹⁰ and solved to first order for d^1 by Ortolano *et al.*¹¹. Thus, in first order the roots for d^9 complexes become

$$E[\Gamma 7^a(^2E_g)] = -6D_q - 2D_s + D_t$$

$$E[\Gamma 6^a(^2E_g)] = -6D_q + 2D_s + 6D_t$$

$$E[\Gamma 7^b(^2T_{2g})] = 4D_q - 2D_s + D_t$$

$$E[\Gamma 6^b(^2T_{2g})] = 4D_q + D_s - 4D_t + \lambda$$

$$E[\Gamma 7^c(^2T_{2g})] = 4D_q + D_s - 4D_t - \lambda/2$$

From these equations using $\lambda = -966 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the crystal field (D_q) and tetragonal distortion (D_s and D_t) parameters were determined (Table 2). The analysis of the spectrum of *o*-ABA-Cu^{II} complex has been carried similarly using $\lambda = -1164 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The colour and electronic spectral data indicate that *o*-ABAH has greater ligand field strength than *o*-ABA.

Table 3. Physical and electronic spectral data for the Cr^{III} complexes

Parameter	[Cr(<i>o</i> -ABA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ SO ₄	[Cr(<i>o</i> -ABAH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃
Colour	Light green	Light blue
μ_{eff} (B.M.)	3.82	3.85
${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}$	11764	11904
${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}$		
${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}$	16447	17730
${}^4T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}$	(*)	23584
${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}$	29069	29671
D_q	1644	1773
B	622	565
β_{35}	0.68	0.62
β_{55}	0.72	0.67

(*) Not clearly identified due to overlapping bands.

The electronic spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes with *o*-ABA and *o*-ABAH were recorded. The colour, peak posi-

tions and crystal field parameters⁹ for these complexes are listed in Table 3.

Also the interelectronic repulsion constants derived from the spin-allowed transition (β_{35}) and that from spin-forbidden transition (β_{55}) were calculated⁹. The data indicate that *o*-ABAH is coordinated to Cr^{III} more covalently than *o*-ABA.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of pure grade. *o*-ABAH was prepared by reported method¹². Metal complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous solutions of CuSO₄ or Cr₂(SO₄)₃ with the ligands dissolved in water in stoichiometric ratios and the mixtures refluxed for ~2 h. On cooling, the separated complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were chemically analysed for C, H, N, and metals. The electronic spectra (NaCl) of the complexes were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer λ_{35} spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy's method.

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